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Development and Validation of Integrative Performance Tasks in Teaching Mathematics 8 of Carig Integrated School: Basis for A Plan of Action

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ABSTRACT

This experimental research aimed to develop and validate integrative performance tasks that can be used as support material in teaching Mathematics 8. The participants of the study were composed of two groups. First, the student participants, one heterogeneous Grade 8 class consisting of 35 students who attended face-to-face classes during the 2022–2023 school year, served as the main subjects of the study. Second, the group of experts was composed of one Mathematics Education Program Supervisor, one OIC Mathematics Department Head, one Mathematics Head Teacher VI, two Mathematics 8 teachers, and two Cluster Head Master Teachers. This group reviewed the pre- and post-tests and assessed the Integrative Performance Tasks in terms of the following characteristics of high-quality assessment: clarity of learning targets, validity, reliability, fairness, practicality, and efficiency.

Results showed that, in terms of the characteristics of high-quality assessment, such as clarity of learning targets, validity, reliability, fairness, practicality, and efficiency, the integrative performance tasks complied to a “*very great extent.*” Moreover, the implementation of the Integrative Performance Tasks significantly improved students' attitudes and performance in a more positive direction. Inferential tests revealed that students' exposure to the Integrative Performance Tasks correlates with their mathematics performance. Among the challenges encountered by students in implementing the IPTs were psychological challenges, confusion in subject integration, and weaknesses in the IPTs themselves. As an offshoot of the study, a proposed plan of action to improve assessment methods in teaching Mathematics 8 was conceptualized and crafted, based on the challenges encountered by the students during the implementation of the Integrative Performance Tasks.

Keywords: attitude, assessment, high-quality assessment, integrative performance tasks, validity

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